

Impact Factor: 5.19

ISSN: 2181-0664

DOI: 10.26739/2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Volume 4, Issue 3

2023

ISSN 2181-0664

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-0664

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

4 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 3

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 3

ТОШКЕНТ-2023

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ | UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL
№3 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0664-2023-3>

Бош мухаррир:
Главный редактор:
Chief Editor:

Мадазимов Мадамин Муминович
Ректор Андижанского Государственного
медицинского института, д.м.н., профессор
кафедры факультетской и госпитальной
хирургии

Тахририят раиси:
Председатель редакционной коллегии:
Chairman of the editorial Board:

Алексеев Андрей Анатольевич
Директор ожогового центра НМИЦ хирургии
им. В.Вишневского, главный комбустиолог
Министерства здравоохранения России, д.м.н.,
профессор.

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Салахиддинов Камалиддин Зухриддинович
доцент, д.м.н. кафедры факультетской и
госпитальной хирургии Андижанского
Государственного медицинского института

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Хегай Любовь Николаевна
доцент, к.м.н., начальник отдела по координации
деятельности грантов Межвузовской научно-
исследовательской лаборатории Ташкентской
медицинской академии

Маъсул котиб:
Ответственный секретарь:
Executive Secretary:

Досина Маргарита Олеговна
в.н.с. ГНУ "Институт физиологии Национальной
академии наук Беларуси", к.б.н., председатель
Совета молодых ученых Отделения медицинских
наук НАН Беларуси

Маъсул котиб:
Ответственный секретарь:
Executive Secretary:

Ниязова Зебинисо Анваровна
PhD кафедры офтальмологии, детской
офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ ТАХРИРИЙ МАСЛАХАТ КЕНГАШИ | РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ EDITORIAL BOARD OF THE UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Хужамбердиев Мамазоир Ахмедович

д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной терапии Андижанского Государственного медицинского института

Привалова Ирина Леонидовна

д.б.н., профессор кафедры нормальной физиологии Курского государственного медицинского университета,
заведующая лабораторией физиологии висцеральных систем НИИ физиологии (Курск)

Гаврилова Елена Анатольевна

д.м.н., профессор, заведующая кафедрой лечебной физкультуры и спортивной медицины Северо-западного
государственного медицинского университета им. И.И. Мечникова (Санкт-Петербург)

Чурганов Олег Анатольевич

д.п.н., профессор кафедры ЛФК и спортивной медицины Северо-Западного государственного
медицинского университета им. И.И. Мечникова (Санкт-Петербург)

Салахиддинов Зухриддин Салахиддинович

д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедры ВОП №1, Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Рябчиков Денис Анатольевич

д.м.н., в.н.с. онкологического отделения хирургических методов лечения ФГБУ "НМИЦ
онкологии им. Н.Н. Блохина" Минздрава России

Гулямов Суръат Саидвалиевич

д.м.н., профессор кафедры оториноларингологии, детской оториноларингологии, стоматологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Тереза Магалхайз
профессор, заведующая кафедрой Судебной медицины государственного университета Порту (Португалия)

Юлдашев Илхом Рузиевич
д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой Аллергологии, иммунологии, микробиологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Хамраев Абдурашид Журакулович
д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной детской хирургии, Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Эрматов Низом Жумакулович
д.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой гигиены детей и подростков и гигиены питания Ташкентской медицинской академии

Рузиев Шерзод Ибодуллаевич
д.м.н., доцент кафедры судебной медицины и медицинского права Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Якубова Олтиной Абдуганиевна
доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии, неонатологии факультета повышения квалификации и переподготовки врачей Андijanского государственного медицинского института

Бабич Светлана Михайловна
доцент, заведующая кафедрой социальной гигиены Андijanского государственного медицинского института

Сабирова Рихси Абдукадировна
д.м.н., профессор кафедры медицинской и биологической химии Ташкентской медицинской академии

Цеомашко Наталья Евгеньевна
д.б.н., с.н.с., заведующая отделом медико-генетических исследований МНИЛ Ташкентской медицинской академии

Хамраева Лола Салимовна
доцент, к.м.н. кафедры офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Усманходжаева Адиба Амирсаидовна
доцент, к.м.н., заведующая кафедрой Народной медицины, реабилитологии и физической культуры Ташкентской медицинской академии

Тухтаева Нигора Хасановна
DSc, доцент кафедры пропедевтики внутренних болезней № 2, Ташкентской медицинской академии.

Шарипова Фарида Камилевна
к.м.н., доцент кафедры психиатрии, наркологии и детской психиатрии, медицинской психологии, психотерапии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Бузруков Батир Тулкунович
д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Туйчиев Галибжан Урмонжонович
к.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой детской хирургии, детской анестезиологии-реаниматологии с курсом
офтальмологии и стоматологии факультета усовершенствования и переподготовки врачей АГМИ

Маматхужаева Гулнора Нажмитдиновна
доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Офтальмологии Андijanского Государственного медицинского института

Каримова Зиёда Кушбаевна
доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Аллергологии, клинической иммунологии, микробиологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Саидходжаева Саида Набиевна
доцент, Phd кафедры неврологии, детской неврологии и медицинской генетики Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Зуфарова Зухра Хабибуллаевна
доцент, к.ф.н. кафедры промышленной технологии лекарственных средств Ташкентского фармацевтического института

Ибрагимова Марина Фёдоровна
PhD, ассистент кафедры N1 педиатрии и неонатологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета.

Алимова Дурдона Дильмуратовна
PhD кафедры оториноларингологии, детской оториноларингологии, детской стоматологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Page Maker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хўршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

МУНДАРИЖА | СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

1. Abdieva Yulduz, Agzamova Gulnara STUDY OF CENTRAL HEMODYNAMICS IN PATIENTS WITH SILICOSIS AND THEIR CORRELATION ANALYSIS WITH MARKERS OF SYSTEMIC INFLAMMATION.....	6
2. Saitnazarov Jamshid, Khaydarov Artur, Kimsanov Shamsiddin, Olimov Azimjon IMPLANTS WITH PARTIAL AND COMPLETE TOOTH LOSS.....	13
3. Irbutaeva Lola, Rasulova Nodira A GENTLE METHOD OF TREATING CHILDREN OF THE FIRST YEAR OF LIFE WITH PERINATAL ENCEPHALOPATHY.....	19
4. Kamilov Haidar, Kamilova Adiba, Rakhimova Raykhon PAIN INTENSITY AND ITS ASSESSMENT IN THE CASE OF GLOSSALGIA.....	23
5. Azizov Abror, Asilova Saodat, Ubaydullaev Bekzod EVALUATION OF THE FUNCTIONAL STATE OF PATIENTS AFTER ARTHROPLASTY WITH ANKYLOSED HIP JOINT.....	28
6. Kamilov Kh.M., Maksudova L.M., Ikramov O.I., Babakhanova D.M., Rustamova K.B. CHOICE OF TREATMENT PATIENTS WITH ENDOPHTHALMITIS.....	39
7. Tulabaeva G.M., Talipova Y.Sh., Sagatova H.M., Abdukadirova N.M., Khusanov A.A. STUDY OF THE HYPOLIPIDEMIC AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY EFFECTS OF “YANTAK” DECOCTION IN PATIENTS WITH CORONARY HEART DISEASE AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF STANDARD THERAPY.....	44
8. Nabieva Shokhista Mustafaevna EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF CHANGES IN THE FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM IN NEWBORNS WITH PERINATAL LESIONS OF THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM.....	53
9. Kamilov Kh.P., Takhirova K.A., Shokirova F.A. MICROBIOLOGICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL FEATURES OF MULTIFORM EXUDATIVE ERYTHEMA OF THE MOUTH.....	60
10. Abdieva Yulduz, Agzamova Gulnara, Mukhlisa Abdullayeva COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF LABORATORY MARKERS IN PATIENTS WITH SILICOSIS WITH LOW AND PRESERVED LVEF.....	65

ISSN: 2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

Kamilov Haidar**Kamilova Adiba****Rakhimova Raykhon**

Tashkent State Dental Institute

komilovaadiba1984@gmail.com

PAIN INTENSITY AND ITS ASSESSMENT IN THE CASE OF GLOSSALGIA

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7875551>

ABSTRACT

Glossalgia is characterized by the periodic appearance of burning, pain and tingling in the tongue, perversion of taste sensitivity, significant prevalence in middle-aged and elderly people and is often combined with somatic diseases. Glossalgia more often affected people aged 60 years and older, mainly women -84.7%, whereas in men this disease was diagnosed in 15.3% of cases, 11.3% were under 40 years old, 21.3% from 40 to 49 years old, 31.3% from 50 to 59 years old and 36% were patients aged 60 or more years.

Keywords: glossalgia, autonomic nervous system, Reducing the intensity of pain, Reducing the intensity of pain

Камилов Хайдар**Камилова Адига****Рахимова Райхон**

Ташкентский Государственный стоматологический институт

komilovaadiba1984@gmail.com

ИНТЕНСИВНОСТЬ БОЛИ И ЕГО ОЦЕНКА У ПАЦИЕНТОВ ГЛОССАЛГИЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Глоссалгия характеризуется периодическим появлением жжения, боли и покалывания в языке, извращением вкусовой чувствительности, значительной распространенностью у людей среднего и пожилого возраста и часто сочетается с соматическими заболеваниями. Глоссалгия чаще поражала лиц в возрасте 60 лет и старше, преимущественно женщин -84,7%, тогда как у мужчин это заболевание было диагностировано в 15,3 % наблюдений, до 40 лет составили 11,3%, от 40 до 49 лет — 21,3%, от 50 до 59 лет – 31,3% и 36% составили больные в возрасте 60 и более лет.

Ключевые слова: Глоссалгия, центральной нервной системой, снижение интенсивности боли, вегетативной нервной системы.

Камилов Хайдар**Камилова Адига**

Рахимова Райхон

Ташкент давлат стоматология институти
komilovaadiba1984@gmail.com

ГЛОССАЛГИЯ БИЛАН ОҒРИГАН БЕМОРЛАРДА ОҒРИҚ ИНТЕНСИВЛИГИ ВА УНИ БАҲОЛАШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Глоссалгия тилда ёниш, оғриқ ва қичишишининг даврий кўриниши, таъмга сезгирликнинг бузилиши, ўрта ва кекса одамларда сезиларли тарқалиши билан тавсифланади ва кўпинча соматик касалликлар билан бирлаштирилади. Глоссалгия кўпинча 60 ва ундан катта ёшдаги одамларга, асосан аёлларга -84,7% таъсир қилади, еракларда еса бу касаллик 15,3% ҳолларда ташхис қўйилган, 11,3% 40 ёшгача, 21,3% 40 ёшдан 49 ёшгача, 31,3% 50 ёшдан 59 ёшгача ва 36% кекса беморлар бўлган 60 ёки ундан ортиқ йил.

Калит сўзлар: Глоссалгия, марказий асаб тизими, оғриқ интенсивлигини камайтириш, автоном асаб тизими.

Introduction. It is proved that glossalgia is the most common neurostomatological disease, accompanied by a decrease in working capacity, mental depression and psychoemotional excitement of patients. General somatic pathology and neurogenic disorders play a leading role in the pathogenesis of glossalgia and glossodynia. Due to anatomical and functional connections with the central nervous system, pathological tonic afferentation into segmental and suprasedgmental structures of the brain occurs.

Glossalgia is characterized by the periodic appearance of burning, pain and tingling in the tongue, perversion of taste sensitivity, significant prevalence in middle-aged and elderly people and is often combined with somatic diseases. Glossalgia more often affected people aged 60 years and older, mainly women -84.7%, whereas in men this disease was diagnosed in 15.3% of cases, 11.3% were under 40 years old, 21.3% from 40 to 49 years old, 31.3% from 50 to 59 years old and 36% were patients aged 60 or more years. [4,7,14].

Glossalgia is characterized by a pain syndrome with a predominance in the language. All these mechanisms eventually lead to the appearance of visceroreflex stem syndrome, namely, to impaired sensitivity and mobility of the tongue, secretory disorders in the oral cavity [9,10,12,13,16].

In pathogenesis, the main role belongs to the state of the autonomic nervous system. These disorders are more often functional than organic in nature [1,3,7,11,15,17]. Other authors, based on modern ideas about the pathogenesis of diseases of the tongue, believe that general factors, such as disorders in the immune system and autonomic nervous system, play an important role in the occurrence of glossalgia. Visual Analog Scale is used to assess pain in practical dentistry. – VAS, Huskisson E.C., 1974) with a sliding ruler, on one (ungraded) side of which the patient indicates a point, in his opinion, corresponding to the severity of BS in the range from 0 (no pain) to 10 cm (unbearable pain), and on the reverse graduated part the doctor fixes the degree of intensity of BS in mm [8].

To improve the definition of the nature of pain and its assessment in the case of glossalgia on the VAS scale.

Material and methods of research:

40 patients aged 35-70 years were examined, 20 of them with glossalgia, a comparison group of 20 healthy individuals served as a control.

To determine the intensity of pain in patients with glossalgia, a visual analog scale VAS – VISUAL ANALOG SCALE-VAS (Huskisson E.C., 1974) was used, the method is carried out by the patient himself on a strip 10 cm long. He is asked to make a mark on the line corresponding to the intensity of the pain he is experiencing. YOUR test is performed on a sliding ruler, on one (ungraded) side of which the patient indicates a point, in his opinion, corresponding to the severity of the pain syndrome in the range from 0 (no pain) to 10 cm (unbearable pain).

Research results and their discussion:

It was found that patients with glossalgia in the study groups evaluated the pain characteristics differently before treatment. Thus, in the control group, in all 20 patients (100.0±0.0), the pain characteristic was mild. The average pain assessment index in the control was 0.05±0.05. In 3 patients of the comparison group (8.11±4.49%), on the VAS scale it was 2.67±0.33 (P<0.01); in 18 (48.65±8.22%) it was moderate, on the VAS scale it was 5.33±0.39 (P<0.001); 16 (43.24±8.14%) had intense pain, according to the VAS scale it was - 7.94± 0.23 (P<0.001). The average pain score in the comparison group was 6.24±0.35 (P<0.001). ($\chi^2= 10,757$; p = 0.005).

Pain characteristics in patients with glossalgia of the main group were mild in 2 (3.92±2.72%), on the VAS scale was 2.50±0.50 (P<0.05); moderate pain was noted in 26 (50.98±7.00%), on the VAS scale was 5.73±0.21 (P<0.001); intense in 23 (45.10± 6.97%), on the VAS scale -8.17± 0.18(P < 0.001). The average pain score in the main group was 6.71±0.25 (P<0.001), ($\chi^2= 20.118$; p = 0.000). The significance of differences in relation to the control group was noted (P<0.001).

In the comparison group, after traditional treatment, after 14 days, the pain intensity on the VAS scale was 3.30±0.36 (P<0.001) points, after 90 days - 2.30±0.36 (P<0.01) points, after 180 days - 1.32±0.21 (P<0.001) points. The average pain score in the group is 3.29±0.28 points. The decrease in pain intensity after 14, 90 and 180 days is 52.88%, 36.85% and 21.15%, respectively, in relation to the indicator before treatment (P<0.001) (Table 1).

Table 1

The intensity of pain according to YOUR in the study groups before and after treatment, M±m

Groups		VASH –visual-analog scale of pain intensity	The average indicator pain assessments in groups
Control, n=20		0,05±0,05	0,05±0,05
Comparisons, n=37	Before treatment	6,24±0,35 ^x	3,29±0,28 ^{*x}
	After treatment, day 14	3,30±0,36 ^{***x}	
	90 days	2,30±0,36 ^{***x}	
	180 days	1,32±0,21 ^{*x}	
Main, n=51	Before treatment	6,71±0,25 ^x	2,71±0,16 ^{*x}
	After treatment, day 14	2,75±0,21 ^{***x}	
	90 days	1,08±0,24 ^{*x}	
	180 days	0,31±0,09 ^{*x}	

Note: * – there was a significant difference in the ratio before treatment (***-P<0.05; **-P<0.01; *-P<0.001); x – in relation to the control group (xxx -P<0.05; xx-P<0.01; x-P<0.001).

In the main group, after complex treatment after 14 days, the pain intensity on the VAS scale was 2.75 ±0.21 (P<0.01) points, after 90 days - 1.08± 0.24 (P<0.001) points, after 180 days - 0.31±0.09 (P<0.001) points. The average pain index in the group is 2.71±0.16 points. The decrease in pain intensity after 14, 90 and 180 days is 40.98%, 16.09% and 4.61%, respectively, in relation to the indicator before treatment (P<0.001). In patients with glossalgia in the study groups, the pain characteristics were re-evaluated after treatment. Thus, in the control group, in all 20 patients (100.0±0.0), the average pain score was 0.05±0.05 (P<0.001).

In 22 (59.46±8.07%) patients of the comparison group, mild pain was noted 14 days after treatment, in 9 (24.32±7.05%) – moderate, in 6 (16.22±6.06%) intense pain was noted. In the comparison group, 90 days after treatment, 24 (64.86±7.85%) had mild pain, 10 (27.03±7.30%) had moderate pain, 3 (8.11±4.49) had intense pain. After 180 days, 28 (75.68±7.05%) had mild pain, 7 (18.92±6.44%) had moderate pain, and 2 (5.41±3.72%) had intense pain. The significance of

differences in relation to the control group and the comparison group ($P < 0.001$) was noted. Pain characteristics after 14 days in patients with glossalgia of the main group were mild in 42 ($82.35 \pm 5.34\%$), moderate pain was observed in 7 ($13.73 \pm 4.82\%$), intense in 2 ($3.92 \pm 2.72\%$). After 90 days, 46 ($90.20 \pm 4.16\%$) have mild pain, 5 ($9.80 \pm 4.16\%$) have moderate pain, there is no intense pain. After 180 days, 51 (100.0 ± 0.00) have mild pain, but there is no moderate and intense pain. The significance of differences in relation to the control group and the comparison group ($P < 0.001$) was noted.

Conclusions:

Thus, after the application of complex treatment with the use of VLOK, it helped to reduce pain in the near and long term. Thus, after treatment in the study groups, especially in pathogenetic treatment in the main group of patients with glossalgia, the pain level after 14 days, 90 days and 180 days was significantly ($P < 0.001$) lower than the baseline, the best result was obtained for reducing the pain level. Reducing the level of pain contributes to an improvement in the quality of life compared to the comparison group who received traditional treatment. A decrease in pain scores 180 days after the treatment dictates the need for treatment at least twice a year, which leads to satisfaction with their overall health and the state of health in the oral cavity.

References.

1. Abdikarimov S.Zh. Assessment of pain syndrome in patients with glossalgia on the Hosslibergman scale. //Science and the world. 2014. Vol. 3. No. 2 (6). pp. 113-115.
2. Abdikarimov S.Zh., Zazulevskaya L.Ya., Bagautdinova B.A. The frequency of dominant complaints in patients with glossalgia depending on the background disease. Science and the World. 2014. Vol. 2. No. 11 (15). pp. 125-128.
3. Abdikarimov S.Zh., Kemelkhan K.Zh., Esmaganbetov S.Sh., Tabaldieva G.H., Zhienbekova M.S. The prevalence of glossalgia depending on the nature of concomitant pathology of the gastrointestinal tract and cardiovascular system. //Bulletin of the Kazakh National Medical University. 2013. No. 1. pp. 111-115.
4. Abdikarimov S.Zh., Sapaeva N.G. Assessment of bioelectric activity of acupuncture points in patients with glossalgia depending on concomitant pathologies. //Science and the World. 2014. Vol. 3. No. 4 (8). pp. 91-93.
5. Aidarov Z.A., Sabirova A.I., Mamytova A.B., Yusupov A.F., Kadyrbaeva A.A. Organizational and methodological aspects of dental care during the pandemic of a new coronavirus infection//The Scientific Heritage. 2020. No. 50-2 (50). pp. 11-17.
6. Borisova E.G. Modern view on the quality of diagnosis of chronic pain syndromes of the tongue. //Fundamental research. 2014. No. 7-2. pp. 246-249.
7. Gileva O.S., Zadorina I.I., Islamova A.F., Plenkina V.A., Sintyurina A.A., Chuprakov M.A. Assessment of pain symptoms in patients with inflammatory diseases of the oral mucosa, parodontal and endodontic // Modern problems of science and education. – 2017. – No. 4.
8. Dychko E.N., Kovach I.V., Sribnik P.L., Vovk V.A. Complex treatment of paresthetic-pain syndrome of SOPR with the use of physiotherapy.//Ukrainian Dental almanac. 2015. No. 1, pp.25-28.
9. Dychko E.N., Kovach I.V., Samoylenko A.V., Romanyuta I.A., Lazerovich A.V. Assessment of the nature of salivation in glossalgia. //Ukrainian Dental almanac. 2010. No. 6. pp. 8-10.
10. Kamilov H.P. Ibragimova M.H., Kamilova A.Z. Determination of discriminatory sensitivity of the tongue in glossalgia in patients who underwent COVID-19 at the stage of rehabilitation//Zh.Medicine and Innovation 2021, No.4, pp.550-555.
11. Lavrovskaya Ya.A., Romanenko I.G., Lavrovskaya O.M., Buglak V.A. Features of clinical manifestations, diagnosis and treatment of glossalgia and glossodynia.// Bulletin of the Medical Institute "REAVIZ", No. 2, 2019.pp.149-154.

12. Starikova I.V., Pitserskaya N.V., Chaplieva E.M., Bobrov D.S. Psychosomatic aspects of diseases of the oral mucosa. //Bulletin of the Volgograd State Medical University. 2021. No. 2 (78). pp. 137-140.
13. Tereshchenko A.V. Glossalgia/glossodynia as an interdisciplinary problem: scientific publication / A.V. Tereshchenko, A. Ya. Dzhappueva // Clinical dermatology and venereology. - M., 2021. - Volume 20 N 1. - C. 19-24.
14. Dim H, Lin S, Thakkar JDC. Neuropathic Pain and Burning Mouth Syndrome: An Overview and Current Update// Dent Clin North Am. 2020 04; 64(2):379-399
15. Fokina NM, Shavlovskaya. Burning mouth syndrome // Zh Neurol Psychiatrist Named After S. S. Korsakov. 2019; 119(1):76-79
16. Jørgensen MR, Pedersen. Analgesic effect of topical oral capsaicin gelin burning mouth syndrome. // Acta Odontol Skand. 2017 Mar; 75(2):130-136

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

4 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 3

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 3

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000